

Brian Paul Kaess Autobiography
by Brian Paul Kaess

‘Lo, the gates of Light have opened before me.’—Manichaeian Psalter

Brian Paul Kaess was born October 24, 1967 in Chicago, Illinois, USA. He was the 1st-born son of Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess & Marie Ellen Dawson. His Identical twin brother was Garret Thomas Kaess. Family lore has it that they were baptized Lutheran- he later attended Protestant churches, including Swedish Protestant (EFCA), University Bible Fellowship (UBF), Jehovah's Witnesses, and even danced with the Mormons. He must have seemed guilty of heresy to the Jehovah's, since he was always *patriotic*. Nonetheless, during his early adulthood, he became *enmeshed* in Protestant ways. Later in life, Brian tried to find proof of his Lutheran baptism in the Chicago area, but the church records appear *patchy* in this regard.

Brian & Garret grew up together and supported each other often. Half-orphans at an early age, newly-widowed Marie and her twins lived in *dire* poverty in neighborhoods such as Uptown& Rogers Park, surviving on public aid. They suffered periods of food insecurity, which was a nice *euphemism* for starvation, and certainly learned the meaning of hard times. This loss of their father Gerd at an early age left a gap in the family until the twins grew up and had families of their own. At such a tender age, Garret and Brian had not yet realized what a flood of calamity had streamed upon them. Garret would practically scoff, 'the best part about family is starting your own!'

In Summer 1977, Illinois Department of Children and Family Services (DCFS) agents and Chicago Police took custody of the twins from Marie (likely for neglect) and they were shuttled through 'the system', first at Uhlich Children's Home, and then with a Foster family (the Larsen's) in Des Plaines, Illinois, before they were happily placed, in Fall 1977, as *Wards of the State of Illinois* with their maternal grandmother Margaret Jane (Swartz) Langley. Coincidentally, they were also in Des Plaines during the same time frame when John Wayne Gasey was 'hunting' his young, male victims. It must have seemed like *poetic* justice years later when he watched the Gasey execution coverage on television with onlookers shouting: 'Gasey- It's time!' Margaret's intervention literally saved the twins.

They thereafter grew up in Edgewater and grew to admire their step-grandfather Norman Allen Langley, a *wiley*-old WWII vet. They were surrounded by many pets and developed an enduring love for cats and dogs. Brian's favorite dogs were Tommy (a blond Labrador mix) and Fuzzy (a white poodle) and his favorite cats were Nieve (i.e. 'Snow'), Candy, baby & Tiger. Candy was the most fortunate pet he ever had, having been taken in as a stray kitten meowing at his front door, and then given food, love, & shelter. Nieve (her name means 'Snow' in Spanish) was brought to him as a kitten from Ramos, gifted by Paul's cousin Regina, and they formed a close bond. Arriving in late November 2020, she was 'hungry from the start,' and Brian always did his best to 'feed her from the hand.' She became just one of his many furry, friends.

Brian & Garret played sports like basketball, football, & baseball, and were *avid* Cubs and Bulls fans. In Fall 1977, they took a trip to Dallas (their 1st air plane flight) to visit their granduncle Francis Aubrey Swartz, who took them to an African-style *safari* and airfield to show them all the planes. They also formed their own baseball team (little-league style) from kids on Hollywood, etc. and had their own dark, navy blue team t-shirts and unique name: *the Hollywood Bombers*. They were narrowly beat in a game by *the Outlaws* when Joanie McMahon made a controversial call as referee in favor of *the Outlaws*. Irish helping Irish!

They enjoyed collecting antique coins too, visiting an antique shop on Western & Devon avenue in the late 1970's. In addition, they had specimens from grandma Margaret's own collection. They also saw *Star Wars* on Western ave. with grandma in the late 1970's when the film first burst upon the scene. Yes, grandma could be hip!

They attended schools like North Shore School, St. Gregory Elementary, and Lane Tech H.S.; Brian's 1st 'Crush' was Regan Phillips at North Shore & Lane (she patently rejected him) and his 1st girlfriend was Kaylynne Miller, Regan's lockermate at Lane. I guess life is full of twists and turns! Brian played on a *High Ridge Chargers* Pop Warner football team that went to Savannah, Georgia, in 1981 and won a national title. He hung out in the back seat with Gigi (a Hispanic girl), his first experience with women. His Prom date in 1985 at Lane was Jennifer Mundt (from Ravenswood). In high school, Brian was a member of the *Gamer's Guild & Lane Tech Marine Fitness Team*, even becoming Captain senior year and winning a 4th place individual trophy in a Chicago-area competition. He was heavily recruited by the U.S. Army & U.S. Marines in high school. He saw the military as a 'way out.' One time, Brian read a book, *Yoni*, about Isreal paratrooper Hero Yoni Netanyahu and became inspired to go to Jump School. He also admired Audie Murphy & George S. Patton. After that, Brian never saw a recruiting office he didn't like! His brother Garret considered enlisting in the Navy but later got an Officer's Commission in the Army instead. Senior Year, Brian signed up for an Airborne-Ranger Medic option with the Army, but it was the Jump School part he was most interested in. Later, at age 28, Brian would sign up for a U.S. Marine Infantry option, and he thereafter became destined to be a U.S. Marine 'grunt.'

In addition, Brian played high school church basketball for First Evangelical Free Church for three years and helped them win a league championship his sophomore year. He even poured in 28 pts. one game his senior year. He obviously did more than just 'grab the pine!' His favorite classes were English, German, Print Shop & History. Math was for the birds!

His circle at Lane included many people such as James Keating, Darlene, Rhonda Wiley, Jennifer Mundt, Kaylynne Miller, Tina (Italian-American), Maria (Greek-American), Mary Alex, Katherine Davis, Bob Gillis, Stephen Michael, John Carl Toth, Chris Aguda, but one cannot say he was too 'popular' or a member of the 'in' crowd. But he seemed to improve academically his Junior and Senior Years and was desirous of finding a way to pay for college. He graduated in the upper half of his class in 1985 with a 24 ACT. The Mundt's (including Jennifer, her sister Heather, & her dad Howard Mundt) & Garret attended his high school graduation at Lane stadium. Jennifer said, 'I'm jealous!' They held a party for him afterwards.

Brian's friends in Chicago included Rafael Cabañin, Hoss, Bob Gillis, Chris Aguda, John Carl Toth, Mike Sutton, John 'Hilmabean' Hillman, Pat Flanagan, Rodney Catayoung, Noel Quintaña, and many more. His nicknames included 'Chaos,' 'Namu', and 'Slime'- none self-appointed. His friends seemed to revel in labeling him with *diminutive* monikers. He almost faltered when he and Mike Sutton made a juvenile mistake by beating up another kid named Ardyle, based on Mike's *prescient* designs, but a caring private attorney (a Vietnam Veteran and former Army Lt. named Jackson) managed to get him a probation deal and he coasted to graduation. The incident with Ardyle turned out to be nothing more than a 'speed bump' to his plans.

He flirted with gang life but fell away due to Christ. He was a member of a street gang called *the Alley Boys* for a few years in his teens, but this was more a *cabal* or clique rather than a gang. They had no gang signs, no tattoos, and no leather jackets to their name. Hence, Brian tried to walk 'the straight and narrow' path but we cannot say that this path was always lit by *sundry* oracles. He survived at least five brutal fights during his youth and early adulthood—one so close to fatal that, like the Manichaeans might say, 'He escaped from death in the midst of the host.' In at least one case, he was probably the victim of his own *truculent* defiance, but no matter. Eventually, he put his troubled past in the rear-view mirror.

Brian can describe his late teen years and early 20's as a sort of *rumspringen* typical not only of some Amish youth, but German-American youth in general- where young people 'run around' but gradually settle down later on.

Brian enlisted in the U.S. Army at age 17 and later served in the Illinois Army National Guard and U.S. Marines (in Cuba). His disposition was such that he was drawn to the military 'like a moth to the flame.' He required grandma Margaret's signature to join, and he thus became an 'emancipated minor' when he entered the military on July 23, 1985. His spiritual journey in Army Basic was such that he felt like he was taking the steps up to Montségur! He was perfect in PT (physical training) and earned a Superior Performance Certificate (or the 'pushups' champion award) for Echo Company in September 1985 at Fort Jackson, S.C., shaking hands with a two-star General and having his name announced to a crowd of soldiers & family spectators as 'Pvt. Brian Kaess from Chicago.' This story strangely never appeared in the newspapers, but because of the many witnesses at the ceremony, this achievement is well-attested. Perhaps a note on this can be found in military personnel records.

Brian's buddies in the Army were Lockery, Wojikowski, Jones, Sayre, Mills, Walker, Niles Arrington, Sgt. Irizarry, Cpl. Roy, SSG Wooden, SFC Fischer, Moton, Lt. Bey, Riddick, Johnson, Garrett, Mitchell, Hernandez, Dejarmin, Black, Vern, and more. Brian was especially proud of his Jump Wings that he earned in 1986 at Fort Benning, Georgia, knowing that it was no handout. Brian kind of 'ate up the Army' and was always trying to better himself. Young soldiers! He also served at Fort Belvoir, Virginia, & Fort Sam Houston, Texas. Furthermore, Brian earned an Army Achievement Medal (AAM) for helping kids after working 'permanent party' at Brooke Army Medical Center in Texas in 1987-88.

His service in the Illinois Army National Guard was brief but he did better in the Marines, for 'one oath does not determine all oaths' as stated in *the Icelandic Sagas*. His reenlistments in the military can be described as a sort of *sisyphean* task. He was a 'Scribe' in Boot Camp for Mike Company at MCRD San Diego in 1997, and was proud to make it through *the Crucible* to earn the title of U.S. Marine. They were always singing the

Marine Corps Hymn in the morning: 'From the Halls of Montezcuma... to the Shores of Tripoli...' He was *ecstatic* to receive his *Eagle, Globe & Anchor* (EGA) and 'warrior's breakfast' after reaching the top of the Reaper! He trained at Camp Pendleton, California at School of Infantry (SOI) West and became a Marine mortarman ten weeks thereafter, despite his injuries. 'Heavy weapons' was now his *forte*.

Brian was happily stunned at orders for Marine Barracks, Cuba, when that came down. He did a year-long stint in Cuba and was medically boarded out at age 31. While there, he experienced a day or two of Hurricane George, that carved through the base like a wrecking ball. He considered himself to be highly motivated and dedicated. His buddies & comrades in the Marines were Lamb, Westover, Facets, Galaz, Delgado (a Christian), Salamanca- Medina, Davenport, Harris, Knox, Foreman, Gower, Barret, Le Clerc, Fleming, LaCount, Van Hoosen, Nichols, Johnson, Sherman, Sgt. George, Sgt. Tejas, SSG Paige, and GySgt. 'Gunny' Jury, Lt. Ring, Capt. Petrucci, Capt. Wallace, Maj. Aiken, Col. Bamford. It was like a 'band of brothers' who picked each other up every time they fell.

His final rank in the U.S. Marines was Lance Corporal and in the U.S. Army his final rank was Specialist-4. His final rank in the Illinois Army National Guard was also Specialist-4 and he never received any disciplinary action during his entire *tenure* in all three branches. Brian's total net service time for active U.S. Army, active U.S. Marine Corps, & the Illinois Army National Guard was 5 years and 27 days. His time in the Illinois National Guard was 8 months and 17 days. He is a U.S. Disabled Veteran (10%). While living abroad, he recalled the U.S. military code of conduct ('I will trust in my God and the United States of America') and the Marine Corps motto: *Semper Fidelis*, which means 'Always Faithful.' Here's to you Devil Dogs!

His 1st wife was Capt. Ellen Byrd Elliott, USAR, RN (Ret.), who he met while stationed at Fort Belvoir, Virginia. Her parents were of English (or longtime American) descent. He knew her initially as an enlisted soldier and NCO, and it was after their divorce that she received her Army Reserve Officer's Commission. She was assigned to a sister unit, the 15th Evacuation Hospital, and they met when she walked up the steps of the enlisted barracks holding her daughter's hand and said 'Hi' to him. They had plans to marry in June/July of 1986, but she backed out with 'cold feet' at the last second. However, when she heard he might put himself on orders for overseas, she reconsidered and practically proposed to him.

They wed on October 10, 1986 (also Heather's Birthday), in front of the Courthouse in Alexandria, Virginia, with an 'old hickory'-style justice of the peace presiding. Ellen had two children from a prior 1st marriage named Steven Ray Ellsberry and Heather Marie Ellsberry, who became Brian's step-children. Brian did not adopt them based on Ellen's wishes to ensure that her 1st husband Douglas Ray Ellsberry paid his child support. They enjoyed watching films like the *The Seventh Sign* (1988) and *Fright Night* (1985) and TV programs like *Tour of Duty* and *Nature*. Brian & Ellen divorced in February 1991 in Xenia, Ohio, because Brian had 'abandoned' the family in 1990 when he left for Chicago, looking for 'greener grass.'

During the Invasion of Panama in late 1989, Ellen was working as an Army Nurse (LPN) at Brooke Army Medical Center in Texas and had been treating wounded soldiers from the conflict. U.S. Pres. George H.W. Bush paid a visit to her Ward and she was among the hospital staff at Brooke that greeted President Bush and she even gave him a hug. She thought he was 'a warm, friendly man.'

He met his second wife, Mayte Urbina Pereda, at Truman College, where she was his ESL student, in Spring 1999. Her 'Hola!' was sophisticated enough for him and she became the 'apple of his eye.' She was an illegal immigrant who had swum the *Rio Bravo del Norte* (*Rio Grande* in English) with a 'coyote' party near Laredo, Texas in about 1997 and worked as a babysitter thereafter. She was *patently* Mexican. They had their 1st date at the *Artists Café* in Chicago, just like Margaret and Talmage. They seemed to get along about Christianity.

Mayte & Brian married in a civil ceremony near *Daley Plaza* in Chicago on July 27, 2000, with much of her family in attendance. So, she became Brian's Mexican-raised better half and, after she became pregnant, they held a baby shower in Summer 2001, sponsored by a Venezuelan doctor Demelean (and his wife Grace) who she babysat for. They thereafter celebrated the birth of a boy, Paul Jesus, on December 11, 2001. This was certainly a 'godsend' for Brian & Mayte- fulfilling their dreams of starting a family. Paul was baptized Roman Catholic in 2003 at *St. Rita of Cascia* church in Chicago, based on Mayte's wishes. Brian figured when he married Mayte, that proved he wasn't a racist, because no racist would ever marry a Mexican. Grandma 'Doris' would've been pleased.

Mayte also made key decisions on Paul's education, he being educated in 'private' schools from K-12. She also obtained Mexican citizenship for Paul based on descent from the mother, applying at the Mexican Consulate in Chicago. They lived in Edgewater & Gage Park from about 2000 to 2006. She became a naturalized USA Citizen on October 25, 2006, in Chicago, sponsored by a 'sweetheart visa' by Brian. They left for Mexico in December, 2006, settling in the state of Durango. They arrived literally at the beginning of the Mexican Drug War, and have 'endured' in Mexico for 18 years so far, with Brian living a *murky*, B. Traven-like existence. So, he has lived in 'semi-retirement' in beautiful, sunny Mexico. Further detail on his & his family's emigration to Mexico can be found in the appropriate report or essay, such as the 'True History.'

Brian holds an A.S. degree from Northern Virginia Community College and a B.A. degree *cum laude* from Northeastern Illinois University. He majored in Philosophy and minored in History. He had a Bosnian-Muslim girlfriend Azra Bojic (Niles West H.S.) while at NEIU and they were *enraptured* for awhile. They enjoyed visiting *Kopi Traveler's Café* in Andersonville and he helped pay for her trip to Paris, as well as helped her graduate. She later married a Bosnian man, but that did not prevent her from becoming his *paramour*. While at Northeastern, Brian was Vice-President of the Philosophy Club. He also studied at the University of Texas at San Antonio and part-time for a Master's in Philosophy at Northern Illinois University Graduate School. His time with the Huskies was far from *prolix*. He left in good standing. So, *in toto*, let beams of shining liberalism flow from a narrow mind!

Brian earned an EMT certificate while in the Army, a DW B1 German Language *Zertificat* (while in Mexico), and attended Spanish Horizons Language School in Lincoln Park (Chicago), studying under Anna Perez of Spain and Ernesto of Mexico. He studied French Appreciation and German in high school and German under Dr. Vicki Tullius at the University of Texas at San Antonio. He also earned a Basic Computer Literacy Certificate at Truman College while he was an ESL Instructor there.

Brian's employment started early with odd jobs such as a Chinese food delivery boy to the Loyola area for Ming's Chop Suey, dishwasher at a Lebanese restaurant, pageboy at Edgewater Hospital, and continued as an adult with roles as a contract security guard at the Midwest Stock Exchange, student-aide at NEIU's Veterans Affairs Office, emergency room registration clerk at Edgewater Medical Center, registrar at Gordon Tech Catholic high school, and ESL instructor at Truman College, City Colleges of Chicago, and even teaching English twice in South Korea (Pusan and Ulsan). At Midwest, he was taken under the wing by Ron Jones (a retired Philadelphia Homicide detective) and even gave stockbrokers \$50 fines for not wearing ties on the trading floor.

He was also a part-time Inbound telemarketer at Direct Response Corp., Inc. in Glenview, IL, a job he helped earn with the assistance of his friend Noel Quintana. Brian was also a part-time ESL instructor in Dist. 214 at Randhurst Mall in Mt. Prospect, IL, and a patient service representative III at Evanston Northwestern Healthcare at their medical office building in Skokie, IL. He was also a security guard for SOA, Inc., working at such sites as Interstate Foods, Inc. and Elek-Tek, Inc.; Interstate was like something out of Upton Sinclair's *the Jungle*, when Brian would walk by steaming, dripping pipes on railcars full of boiling chemicals. He was a security guard for Stanley Smith, Inc. in San Antonio, TX, where he worked sites in Alamo Heights, golf tournaments, and at the old *Texas Military Institute*, Douglas MacArthur's *alma mater*. Becoming a registrar at Gordon Tech High School and an ESL instructor at Truman College, located in Uptown, where he and Garret had grown up in irksome poverty, must have seemed like a *parvenu*-style achievement to him. This was probably the *zenith* of his professional career.

When his friend Bob Gillis asked him how he obtained the job at Gordon, Brian replied simply: 'I threw my hat in the ring.'

He was an asst. coach for the Chess Club at Gordon and an asst. coach for their Speech and Debate team. He worked closely with head coach Cindy Fey and they both went together on a road trip to Springfield, Illinois, where the team competed and they were Finalist Judges for the *Illinois Speech-and-Debate Finals*. Brian was happy he and the G.T. Rams were able to make it 'downstate' to Springfield! Go Rams!

A milestone occurred when he *reunited* with his German family in the Neckar Valley in 1990, practically taking an ancestral village tour early in life, literally meeting his relatives & their neighbors in the process. It was surely a shock for my German grandparents and aunts when they received news of myself and Garret- alive and well in Chicago! Arnhild almost caused an incident at the Stuttgart airport in 1990, when she practically rushed through a 'security gate' to hug Brian.

The people he met during my 1st trip to Europe included half-aunts Arnhild Kaess (whom he exchanged letters) & Ursula Kaess, grandpa Paul Ernst Kaess, step-grandma Hildegard Golz Kaess, cousins Dr. Anke Theilacker, her husband Stefan, cousins Tatiana & Boris Christmann, granduncle Eduard Dorschke and his daughter Inge Dorschke, and neighbor Sven Urbaschek. Brian must have felt like a *prodigal* son. He enjoys maintaining contact with them 'across the pond.'

Through them he and Garret were also able to make contact with Kulhanek cousins in the SW suburbs of Chicago: Daria Meyer & husband Manfred Meyer, Anita Szymczak, Elsa & Ron Burmas, Roland Kulhanek, his wife Shirley Bunch (from Mississippi), cousins Greg Kulhanek & Kimberly Kulhanek, and cousins Richard Kulhanek & Jeffrey Eugene Kulhanek. Garret and Brian attended Kimberly Kulhanek's wedding party to Ron Kohs in 2000. He has located new relatives since doing genealogy such as cousins Melanie Dorshke, Uwe Dorschke, Beate Stromsky, Adriana Engelbart (of Brazil), & Monica Fercho (of Canada), plus many more.

He has visited the *Eiffel Tower*, *Brandenberg Gate*, *Neuschwanstein Castle* & *Untersberg Peak*, as well as paying for his own eurorailing and backpacking trips to Europe. He felt like the *czar* of 'shoestring' travel, giving himself the *sobriquet* of 'Travel Master.' Staying in youth hostels, he must have sighed: 'I traversed all places in haste, I found no haven save Christ,' *per* the ancients.

Brian was appointed to a U.S. Selective Service Board in 2006 as a volunteer Local Board Member in Chicago, and prided himself on this achievement until illness came along and prevented him from attending his 1st meeting at UIC. The arrival of ill health, in this regard, as with his military disabilities, was most *unpropitious*. Despite these setbacks, Brian remained *patriotic*.

He even did part-time missionary work for *University Bible Fellowship* (UBF) in Pusan, South Korea, when he first taught in 1996-97. His bible teachers were Theresa Sohn & her husband Dr. Augustine Sohn of UBF Chicago. He also knew Mary and Kim Daniel of UBF Pusan. He had a Korean girlfriend named Kim Ryung in Pusan. She was a PNU grad. They saw *Romeo and Juliet* (1996) and *The Rock* (1996) together when these films came out in South Korea. He took a liking to mountain-trekking and climbed Mt. Gaji in 2002 of his own accord, even though he was a disabled vet. He also had a 'penpal' named Marys Desaulniers (who he met in Salzburg) and visited her twice in Cap-de-la-Madeleine, touring Montreal and Quebec City in the process. She was a student at Concordia University in Montreal. In Salzburg, he also met a Czech girl named Lucia, and Stephanie Kramer in a laundry mat in Berlin. He communicated with Tisha Stapleton in West Virginia, a sincere Christian girl. Her emails improved his *morale* in the Marines- he didn't know Christians still existed!

So, you can easily say, Brian was a 'ladies man' in his 20's and early 30's. There was Isolde Kohn from Magdeburg, Germany (introduced by John Toth), Anja Zeigler from Stuttgart (hand-picked by Arnhold Kaess), Katherine Davis from Chicago (who said to Brian: 'I knew you were cool!'), Cindy Bradley of Davenport, Iowa (he met her at *Neo* nightclub), Heidi Blaumueller of Lake Zurich, Illinois (also introduced by John Toth), & Susanne Dagroot of Arlington Heights, Illinois. Heidi was rumored to have given birth to his *illegitimate* son Joshua Blaumueller, but little else is known, and Brian prays he has not been kept in the dark.

His friend John Toth also set him up with Lisa, a mutual friend of John and Edie's. She was from the NW suburbs. Then there was Stella, a teenager he hung with at the Lake, who was college-bound to Marquette. She gave him a ride one day and demanded a number. There was also Susanna, a woman he hung out with at the lake as well, who stated *emphatically*: 'I know Brian liked me!' He dated Michelle Moran in 1992 and they went to the horse racing track with her friends. He dated Mary Alex (a Greek girl and Lane student) & Zlata Boras (a Croatian girl & future Depaul grad) when he was on leave

from the Army. Zlata surely didn't like it when he married Ellen. He also went dancing to *the Smart Bar* in Chicago with Beth, a suburban Jewish girl, & her friend Lena (a Loyola Med student), a *vexed* date for Garret. He visited Beth's house in the suburbs, but she eventually moved to Florida. Garret didn't help things by telling Brian to 'break it off' with Beth. Meeting all these women must have made him feel 'his chalice was lit.'

He also dated Vicki Valencia (Lane *alum*), Melissa (CNA), & Kathy (R.N.) from Edgewater Medical Center where they all worked. Little happened with Vicki and Kathy was going through a divorce but he 'wrapped' pretty good with Melissa at *the Crobar* nightclub one night. There were also Loyola gals such as Emily Brown, Mara Pallasch, Jane, Kate Hennehan, Aaron, Nancy Sullivan, etc., but these were mostly folks he bumped into at *Hamilton's Bar* and shared a beer with. He hung out at parties with an Irish girl named Leann he met at *PC's (the Pumping Company)* bar on Broadway. In his teens, he had hung out with Anna Mikan and her brother Joe's entourage. With his friend Schroeder, he went horseback riding in Wisconsin with Marie (a Phillipina girl) & her sister and also on a trip to Northern Michigan U. in Marquette. He knew them all from Edgewater. While at Truman, he dated Chau Nguyen (of Vietnam), & Ruby Khan, who claimed to be a Princess of Bangladesh.

Moreover, he met Symea (of Bosnia) in the elevator at his apartment building, and she also happened to be a Truman student. In addition, he went ice-skating with Victoria Brown (of Ukraine) and Gloria Pozo- Victoria could easily pass as a James Bond girl! He considered marrying Ruby Khan, but like Stan Kerr used to say, 'if wishes were horses, we'd all be princes!' In the end, he married Mayte, who seemed more earnest than the rest. She must've got the word: 'when you marry a Marine, you get citizenship!'

He embraced the *Alternative* music scene for awhile and saw *the Cure* in concert with Mayte in Summer 2000 in Tinley Park, Illinois at the now-defunct World Music Theatre. He also saw Tina Turner at Neckar stadium in 1990 with aunts Ursula & Arnhild. Arnhild took him to a weird sex museum called the Koons Museum in Stuttgart. Brian knows you shouldn't mix music and art, but he thought the Ozuna video 'Una Locura' was a Dali! He enjoyed taking Mayte and Paul to *Zephyrs* ice-cream parlor (now closed) in Ravenswood, where they had the works. Jennifer had taken him there in high school (after her performance in the school play) when they were dating. Compared to her, he must have felt like Molly Tibbetts' dumb boyfriend. He also attended book readings and discussions at *Nextbook Jewish Literature Series* in Chicago from about 2002-2006, but Brian is not really Jewish in any significant way, except for a hint of ancestry many generations before. He even took Mayte to see the *Chicago Symphony Orchestra* in concert at Orchestra Hall in Fall 2000. Brian would also visit *Facets Multi-Media* Film Center in the Depaul area, even taking Mayte once to see *avante-garde* films at the *Latino International Film Festival* held there. So, in a way, he 'walked the streets of Babylon', quoting St. Augustine's *Confessions*.

Brian had minor surgery on his toes to remove ingrown toenails (whose existence might have disqualified him from military service) and was able to enlist in the U.S. Army successfully as a result. Brian put on dental braces in about Sept. 1995 and had them taken off in Sept. 1996. They helped straighten out his dental profile. He was disqualified from joining the U.S. Army (for a year) in Nov. 1, 1995, for wearing dental braces, but later successfully enlisted in the U.S. Marines in March 1997. His leg was

injured during training and he had a right finger broken by the end of Infantry School. Both later qualified for disability ratings. Brian's leg/knee injuries during his time in the service were like the Union lines at Gettysburg: 'They buckled, but did not break!' After the service, he developed type-2 diabetes at age 47. In any case, he thought diabetes was a cute, 'sweet-tooth' disease. Like they say in the movies: 'It's not the years, it's the mileage!'

Brian spent two weeks in the *sanitarium* (Madden mental health facility) in Maywood, Illinois, in September 2003, based on a domestic violence complaint, but the charges never made it to court and Brian returned to his family. Based on a suggestion from a black social worker (and NEIU *alum*), he was able to apply for and receive SSDI and was better able to support his family. While at Madden, he witnessed a small-time 'breakout,' but did not participate. He also receives a VA disability check.

At his Lane Tech high school 20th annual reunion in Rosemont, Illinois, in 2005, he was able to mingle with *alumni* such as Darlene Wywialowski (a Polish gal), Rhonda Wiley (retired Air Force 1st Sgt.), Doris Chin (former Marine Sgt.), & Stuart Eng (Lane football Captain). He got word of the Lane Tech 40th Annual reunion in 2025, from his friend Chris Aguda but he did not attend as he was firmly established with family in Mexico.

So, while in Mexico, Brian decided to do more than just 'whittle away his time,' and got down to work as a pauper-genealogist. He didn't have much money, but plenty of enthusiasm! So, his time in Mexico no longer became a 'herald of decline.' Hence, Brian is a genealogy enthusiast and has written newsletter/journal articles, at least one poem, other lines of poetry, a collection of essays, academic-minded articles, a history of his time in Mexico, and even some family books on occasion.

His father, Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess, emigrated from West Germany, with ancestral ties to the Neckar Valley, as well as Upper Silesia, and distant ancestors in Ukraine. His American grandmother Margaret's family was from the Shenandoah Valley, Virginia and she *doted* about her early life growing up near the Natural Bridge to the twins. Brian is also a direct descendant of Rev. John Nicholas Kurtz, D.D., of Lützellinden, Hesse, Germany- the 1st Lutheran pastor ordained in America. Like the old saying goes: 'All I know is, they were from Germany!'

Brian became interested in genealogy in Summer 2010 when he visited the *Newberry Library* in Chicago. In 2011, Brian was offered a free membership to the *Sons of Confederate Veterans* (SCV) by Gale Red during the Sesquicentennial of the *American Civil War* (ACW). Heritage, not Hate! Gail began helping Brian nail down his genealogy. His relatives gave him excellent leads too. In this regard, he has received help from Arnhild Kaess, Ursula Kaess, & Paul Ernst Kaess, especially when Paul handed over a heirloom of valuable vintage black-and-white photos and genealogy papers to Brian when he was in Europe in 1990. These items are in the possession of Garret Thomas Kaess of Indianapolis, Indiana.

Also helpful were cousins Melanie Dorschke (of Germany), Tatiana Poesler, Ester Kaess (of Germany), Johanna (of Poland), Edyta Zadworna (of Poland), near-relative Dirk Wendland (regarding Czech records), Brenda Dulaney (regarding Confederate yarns), Lynette Browning Winterton (of Utah), Jeanene Michelle Forshey (regarding a Finnish connection), Sister Elizabeth Anne Swartz (the Swartz family historian), Bryan Francis Swartz (regarding his father Francis Swartz' wartime exploits), Hugh Malone

Swartz (on the Eschenfelters of Germany), Clayta Bryant of the *Haller-Gibboney Rock House Museum*, Barbara Piasecka of Polish Origins, Julie Busse of the Wilmette Family Search Center, and many more.

Brian also became a member of the *Military Order of Stars and Bars* (MOS&B) and a Village Coordinator for Sarata, Gnadental, & Lichtental in South Russia (now in present-day Ukraine) for *American Historical Society of Germans from Russia* (AHSGR). The latter membership he had won at *Rootstech 2024*. He has also been a member of the *Germanic Genealogy Society* (GGS), *The Mid-Atlantic Germanic Society* (MAGS), the *Southwest Florida Germanic Genealogy Society* (SWFLGGS) (now defunct) and the *Polish Genealogical Society of America* (PGSA). Moreover, Brian is a member of *American Veterans for Ukraine* (AVU) and a fan of Vladimir Zelensky, who he considers to be 'very churchillian,' in Geraldo's words.

Brian's greatest achievement in genealogy, in coordination with his Polish & German cousins, was probably helping to develop his Silesian (or Polish) side of his family tree to the 3rd-10th gr. grandparents. This took painstaking work over a number of years. Next in line was finding the only known image or photo of his American grandpa Talmage Edward Dawson in a U.S. Govt. OPF (Official Personnel Folder) file, which he had rightly suspected might be there. He also aided his brother Garret Thomas Kaess in his application for German Citizenship, by timely handing over his dad's and grandpa's German birth certificates.

Brian believes there also may be a direct connection to Jacob Luther, sibling to the famed pastor Martin Luther, through his Marstaller/Marsteller ancestors of Pfungstadt, Hesse, Germany. He also may have located an ancestor or possible set of ancestors for John Swartz of Virginia, the earliest known Swartz ancestor, named Phineas Swartz, but this needs further analysis to verify. He was also able to *crystallize* his knowledge of his Confederate ancestors, especially Robert E Gibboney, Maj. William Gibboney, Pvt. Joseph Godfrey Swartz, Capt. John Haller Gibboney & Pvt. Albert Haller Gibboney- all from Virginia. With the aid of his wife's Mexican family members, such as Dr. Juan Urbina and Abilena Lozano Bueno, he was able to find a *cluster* of Ocón/Urbina siblings that matched the names/location described in a family interview, and thereby solidify and tap into preexisting lines, thereby breaking through a 'brick wall' on the Mexican side of the family tree.

Brian, with the help of cousin Beate Stromsky, was able to further build the Kaess surname line, and learn of their descent from Ludwig I, Count of Württemberg-Urach (1412-1450), a 'gateway' ancestor to Charlemagne, 'the Father of Europe.' On grandma Margaret's side, he connected in to the Coffman/Kauffman line of the Family Hart database, thus confirming Swiss ancestry. Furthermore, he has done GR (or German-Russian) research on Kaess distant cousins who lived in what is now Ukraine (once South Russia), with the help of Dr. Erika Bravo at Texas A & M University. He also pinned down the year (1902) his Kansas ancestor David Bennett Dawson had died in a railway accident. And touchingly, he re-discovered Kim Parker's research on his Virginia ancestor Frances Ann Haller Gibboney, who painted beautiful *vistas* of Southwest Virginia at the turn of the century. Brian counts about 40 U.S. Presidents as relatives, mostly from his mom's side.

Brian leaned Democrat politically but has been known to root Republican on occasion. He finds President Trump's *expansionism* interesting. He admired Ronald Reagan for his buildup of the military. He voted for Mitt Romney (R-UT) because he was a 'good man.' He even shook hands with Bobby Rush (D-IL) on State Street in Chicago in November 1998 mere days after coming home from the U.S. Marines and has chatted with Leslie, an aide to Rep. Jan Shakowsky (D-IL). He also voted for Bill & Hilary Clinton.

He even knew Micky Flanagan (R-IL) in high school & college. He also mingled with Ward Committeeman John Prado (D-IL) of the 14th Ward during election time, who was happy to guide Brian in voting. He even witnessed Alderman Edmund Michael Burke (D-IL) of the 14th Ward sitting in his office, while glued to his desk, during a visit to register to vote. Brian also knew Michelle (Aguda) Clancy, future Porter County (Indiana) Treasurer (D-IN), in high school and college and was her roommate for 3 ½ years when he was a young, struggling college student. He continues to support Isreal, NATO, Japan & South Korea and all friends and allies of the USA. Let us hope that Brian's early *liberalism* serves as a reliable attestation of his views on politics.

Brian had read that half-orphans and orphans could be ferocious about genealogy later in life, and he certainly fits that *vein*. Brian spent his final years amid *festal* days & holiday parties, *eager* to contribute to the sum total of his family's well-being & happiness, and always ready for new tasks. It would have been no surprise to him if Fate would have drawn him elsewhere in his last years. Always *resilient*, Brian reveled in turning failure into success, and family was often the *lens* by which he viewed the world and his one last enduring comfort. Like the lines in a poem he had once written to his half-aunt Ursula: 'little did she know her nephew was Parsifal in disguise.'